

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.451 Max: 63.6099	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1169 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
				In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	
DEFINITION Yellowish layer north of wall 1135				Covered by #SU: 1016	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay 15% silt 80% sand 5% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery m <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles m <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae m <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster R <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone R <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal R <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
					Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				cut by 1170		
Western Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				cut by 1175		
Eastern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				cut by 1152		
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by: 1214			Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1016			Covers: 1211, 1212, 1187, 1222			
Is cut by: 1152, 1170, 1175, 1209			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS - excavated with pick axes; N limit of SU difficult to distinguish from 1214. Its contact with the lower yellow layer below is diffuse in that the bottom half of 1169 starts to become yellow.						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: located immediately north of 1135 and stretches the entire length of the structure Shape: linear shape; roughly square						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): This layer appeared to be brown in color, with no noticeable slope. A bit of rubble layer below visible on EN side.						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): This layer contained pottery and amphorae sherds. Rubble was granular and easy to travel.						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): thicker along the S; thinner in NE corner where layer of rubble and tile appears.						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight						
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:	Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)
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INTERPRETATION

layer probably represents colluvium from post-abandonment of structure. this is suggested by its rubble and fragmented pottery inclusions and the silty nature of the soil as well as the layer's homogeneity.

SOIL SAMPLING: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): 2 Sample quantity (buckets): good → from centre of depth Sample fraction (%): 29%	NON SOIL SAMPLES: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.): Size:	SIEVING: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):
STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor	Filled-out by <i>Dominic Francis</i> on <i>12-7-10</i> Revised by <i>LMB</i> on <i>22.07.10</i> PDFd by <i>JSM</i> on <i>23.07.2010</i> Entered by _____ on _____	